

Dehydration of plant cells shoves nuclei rotation allowing for 3D phase-contrast tomography

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Abstract

Single-cell phase-contrast tomography promises to become decisive for studying 3D intracellular structures in biology. It involves probing cells with light at wide angles, which unfortunately requires complex systems. Here we show an intriguing concept based on an inherent natural process for plants biology, i.e. dehydration, allowing us to easily obtain 3D-tomography of onion-epidermal cells' nuclei. In fact, the loss of water reduces the turgor pressure and we recognize it induces significant rotation of cells' nuclei. Thanks to the holographic focusing flexibility and an ad-hoc angles' tracking algorithm, we combine different phase-contrast views of the nuclei to retrieve their 3D refractive index distribution. Nucleolus identification capability and a strategy for measuring morphology, dry mass, bio volume and refractive index statistics are reported and discussed. This new concept could revolutionize the investigation in plant biology by enabling dynamic 3D quantitative and label-free analysis at sub-nuclear level using a conventional holographic setup.

1. Introduction

Optical microscopy of transparent biological specimens is mostly governed by two outstanding concepts, namely marker-based and label-free imaging. Both are devoted to induce a contrast mechanism to enable the visualization of all the sample structures that are transparent at the wavelength of the light probe. Marker-based imaging relies on dyes and various contrast agents to excite fluorescence in some sample areas. Specific information can be gained by accurately changing the marker, in order to excite the sole sub-cellular structures of interest. On the other hand, label-free methods are noninvasive and do not require markers, simplifying sample preparation at the cost of specificity, and avoiding any possible toxicity effect of the contrast agent. In particular, Quantitative Phase Imaging (QPI) relies on the phase-contrast between the sample and the surrounding medium to image transparent structures, which in turn is due to refractive index differences¹⁻³. Digital Holography (DH) in microscope configuration is one of the preferred label-free

40 techniques to image biological samples in the form of confluent cell layers, tissues, and suspended cells in high-
41 throughput microfluidic streams. DH gives access to the sample complex amplitude, from which the phase-contrast map
42 can be measured⁴⁻⁸. The digital hologram of the sample can be captured out-of-focus, and then digitally refocused in
43 post-processing by numerically solving the diffraction integral that simulates the process of wavefront propagation. DH
44 is well assessed and has been deeply exploited in all fields of biology, diagnostics and medicine, microfluidics and lab-
45 on-a-chip imaging, 3D tracking, cell mechanics, point-of-care testing, environmental monitoring⁴⁻¹⁴. In DH, the
46 measured quantitative information is the optical thickness contrast, which is the integral product between the sample
47 refractive index contrast and its physical thickness along the optical axis. In order to decouple this information, multiple
48 channels have to be exploited, e.g. multiple wavelengths or illumination angles¹⁵. In particular, Phase-Contrast
49 Tomography (PCT) probes the sample from different directions to achieve resolving capability along the optical axis
50 and to measure the sample refractive index 3D distribution¹⁶⁻²². Multi-angle illumination can be realized by moving the
51 light source with respect to the object^{16,17}. Recently, in-flow cytotomography has been demonstrated by inducing
52 controlled sample rotations in microfluidic streams, which is advantageous to maximize the throughput²². Several
53 works have been proposed over the years to enhance the performance of DH imaging, e.g. aimed at increasing spatial
54 and temporal resolution, Field of View (FoV), depth of focus and signal-to-noise ratio^{10,23-25}. However, due to the
55 limited sensitivity of any optical system and the intrinsic sensor quantization, our capability to observe tiny inner
56 structures of the sample depends on the refractive index contrast itself. In the case of thin tissue slices, confluent cell
57 layers or cells spread onto LoC substrates, refractive index plays the major role in determining the observed phase-
58 contrast. In the absence of an adequate refractive index difference between the structure of interest and the surrounding
59 medium, even high spatial resolution is not sufficient to guarantee neither a correct quantitative phase-contrast mapping
60 nor tomographic imaging. In order to improve the phase contrast, the use of dyes or the intracellular injection of
61 glycerol, genetically encoded agents or other strategies for DH microscopy have been proposed²⁶⁻²⁸. Here we
62 deliberately induced dehydration in epidermal onion cells and exploit it to achieve a more convenient imaging condition
63 in 3D. In fact, we show that dehydration provokes the progressive loss of intracellular water content inducing rotation
64 of the cell nucleus over a wide range of angles thus permitting us the accomplishment of 3D imaging by PCT without
65 any mechanical or electro-optical laser beam scanning device. We studied the dehydration process through DH time-
66 lapse experiments and we determined an optimal time window to observe the sample before plasmolysis starts. In other
67 words, the process we have induced is reversible within the selected time-window and thus can be used to improve 3D
68 imaging by PCT in nondestructive manner. We demonstrate in the following that the concept of controlled dehydration
69 allows us to access the nucleolus of onion epidermal plant cells and to measure its 3D properties in simple mode. Plant
70 cells contain the vacuole, i.e. a roundish tank surrounded by the tonoplast membrane. In a mature plant cell, the vacuole
71 occupies between the 80% and the 90% of the internal cell volume and is responsible for turgor pressure. Turgor
72 pressure gives solidity to the cell and is generally determined by the water content of the vacuole (see Supplementary
73 Information). By controlling the environmental temperature and humidity, we alter the cell turgor through the variation
74 of its aqueous content, as sketched in Fig. 1a. Moreover, we make use of 3D finite-element Direct Numerical
75 Simulation (DNS) to furnish a simplified description of the fluid dynamics inside onion epidermal cells during
76 dehydration. Results show that, upon the dehydration process starts, curved streamlines develop in the liquid inside the
77 cell. This explains at glance why the nucleus begins to rotate, as clearly observed in our experimental tests. At the same
78 time, dehydration also leads to a rearrangement of the cytoskeletal structures and to a relaxation of the mechanical
79 constraints that keep the nucleus fixed in its initial position²⁹⁻³², thus promoting its rotation. Here we demonstrate that,
80 when specific conditions are met, it is possible to exploit this induced rotation to accomplish PCT of the nuclei. It is

81 important to underline that the rotations experienced by the nuclei occur spontaneously, they are unknowns of the
82 problem we tackle, and the corresponding angles are difficult to be measured. Nonetheless, thanks to the unique 3D
83 imaging features of a digital holographic microscope, we show that it is possible to retrieve accurate 3D positions and
84 angles of the nuclei during their rotation^{33,34}. For this purpose, we develop an ad hoc angle tracking algorithm to
85 estimate the rotation angle, that is unknown but essential for any tomographic reconstruction. Finally, from the 3D
86 tomograms, we identify the nucleolus and, for the first time to the best of our knowledge, we measure its refractive
87 index, dry mass, 3D morphological features, and bio-volume with a label-free and non-invasive method. Plant cells'
88 taxonomy, physiology, reproduction, and evolution are topics deeply studied in all fields of botany and agriculture,
89 ecology and animal biology, pharmacology and medicine, food production and smart farming. The actin cytoskeleton of
90 plant cells is known to play a key role in the morphogenesis and function of highly specialized cell types, and to drive
91 cytoplasmic streaming^{35,36} and mitochondrial movement³⁷. Thus, it is of interest to dynamically track in 3D
92 intracellular movements and cell trafficking processes with transport of biological material. In particular, imaging onion
93 cells is convenient since onion epidermis shows large transparent cells in a monolayer and exhibit a clearly identifiable
94 mitotic process^{38,39}. On the other hand, because of their high number of rRNA genes and the large size of the dense
95 fibrillar component mass inside the nucleus, onion cells are the most appropriate samples for studying plant viruses⁴⁰
96 and immunolocalization⁴¹. It is worth remarking that this simple strategy we propose is fully reversible as we were able
97 to observe wide angle rotation before the plasmolysis event. Thereby, the dehydration process can be stopped before the
98 cells experience irreversible damages. This means the sample could be brought back to its normal healthy state by
99 reversing the dehydration process after the tomographic shooting.

101 2. Results

102 2.1. Phase-contrast optimization by induced dehydration

103 We performed a long-time lapse of an onion epidermal cells' layer by a holographic microscope in off-axis
104 configuration. We recorded 203 holograms, one every 6 minutes, using the experimental DH setup described in the
105 Materials and Methods section. Thus, we observed the dehydration of the onion cells for about 20 hours. For each
106 recorded hologram, we applied conventional DH processing (see Materials and Methods), and we obtained the
107 corresponding Quantitative Phase Maps (QPMs). In Figure 1b, from left to right, we show four QPMs taken at times 0
108 h, 10 h, 15 h and 20 h, respectively. Moreover, we highlight in red the cell wall of three cells and in green, cyan, and
109 yellow the corresponding protoplast after the plasmolysis has occurred, i.e. at $t_{p1} = 12.9$ h for the first cell, $t_{p2} = 12.2$ h
110 for the second cell, and $t_{p3} = 10.5$ h for the third cell. It is clear that in onion epidermal cells plasmolysis is convex, as
111 reported also in bright field and fluorescence images⁴². During the dehydration, loss of the cell sap and in turn reduction
112 of the turgor pressure occur. We can evaluate the temporal trend of the phenomenon by monitoring the phase-contrast²⁸
113 in the holographic reconstructions. Indeed, the evaporation of the aqueous content makes the image contrast increase.
114 For each QPM, we evaluate the global image contrast as the sum of the modulus of its Laplacian. We report it in the top
115 of Fig. 1c, normalized between 0 and 1. The global normalized gradient is fitted well by a logistic function that is
116 overlapped in red to the measured values. It is reasonable to expect that the plasmolysis takes place when the rate of
117 aqueous loss is maximum. As shown by the vertical lines, the plasmolysis of the three cells occurs in correspondence
118 with the region of maximum slope, i.e. the region in which the growth rate of the image contrast is maximum, as also
119 confirmed by the differential global normalized contrast in the bottom of Fig. 1c. This is reasonable since plasmolysis is
120 a breaking event in the dehydration process that should correspond to the highest increment of the function that
121 describes the loss of turgor pressure. In other words, the logistic function and its time derivative are found here to

122 describe quite well the ongoing dehydration process and how it leads to the plasmolysis. Finally, in Figure 1d, for each
 123 of the three cells, we show the temporal trend of the percentage ratio between the protoplast area, A_P , and the cell area,
 124 A_C . After plasmolysis, these trends are fitted well by a linear function (in red), whose angular coefficient is reported in
 125 black for each cell. Supplementary Movie 1 shows the complete time-lapse from which the maps in Fig. 1b are
 126 extracted, along with the corresponding analysis shown in Fig. 1c and Fig. 1d.

127

128 **Fig. 1.** (Supplementary Movie 1) **Exploiting induced dehydration in onion epidermal cells.** **a** Sketch of the induced
 129 change in a cell turgor pressure due to the cell aqueous content. Cell dehydration can be induced acting on the
 130 environmental temperature, T, and Humidity, H. The released nucleus is free to move and rotate. Dehydration also
 131 allows imaging the cell with enhanced phase contrast, thus boosting the optical system sensitivity. Within the
 132 observation window, nucleus rotation is exploited for PCT. **b** Four QPMs at different times with the cell walls
 133 highlighted in red and the corresponding cell membranes after the start of plasmolysis shown in green, cyan, and
 134 yellow. **c** Top: Global image contrast normalized between 0 and 1, with the logistic fitting overlapped in red. Bottom:

135 Differential global normalized contrast, i.e. the time derivative of the logistic function, whose peak marks the breaking
136 plasmolysis event. The vertical lines correspond to the plasmolysis times, i.e., $t_{p1} = 12.9$ h for the first cell, $t_{p2} = 12.2$ h
137 for the second cell, and $t_{p3} = 10.5$ h for the third cell. **d** For each cell, temporal trend of the percentage ratio between the
138 protoplast area, A_P , and the cell area, A_C , with a linear fitting overlapped in red. Values at the top right corner are the
139 angular coefficients of the linear fitting after the plasmolysis event.

140

141 **2.2. Modeling induced dehydration and plasmolysis**

142 The cytoskeleton is a network composed by three types of protein fibers, which extend from the nucleus to the cell
143 membrane within the cytoplasm, namely intermediate filaments, microfilaments (or actinic filaments), and
144 microtubules. In particular, the intermediate filaments have a purely structural role because they create a support
145 scaffold inside the cell. Therefore, they avoid the movements of some organelles, including the nucleus. The
146 cytoskeleton has specific biomechanical properties²⁹ and it reorganizes itself when the plasmolysis occurs³⁰⁻³². As
147 discussed above, the reduction of cell turgor associated to dehydration makes the intermediate filaments blocking the
148 nucleus relax, thus allowing for its movement. In order to investigate whether fluid dynamic conditions for nucleus
149 rotation might establish during cell dehydration, we performed 3D finite-element DNS of a simplified system
150 mimicking an onion epidermal cell through the commercial software COMSOL Multiphysics™ V5.5 (details on the
151 mathematical model are given in the Supplementary Information). In Figure S2, we report the initial geometry of the
152 computational domain, i.e., a prism containing water with shape similar to cell 1 in Fig. 1. Simulation was divided into
153 two different parts. Supplementary Movie 2 shows the first part in which the simulated cell undergoes dehydration
154 before the plasmolysis event, i.e. $t < t_p$. In this stage, dehydration was simulated by considering water evaporation
155 through the top surface parallel to the xy-plane, whereas the other surfaces of the solid figure were considered to be
156 impermeable. Upon beginning of dehydration, the cell started deflating, as highlighted in Fig. 2a by the decrease of the
157 cell's height in the z-direction at three increasing values of time before plasmolysis. Supplementary Movie 3 shows the
158 case of a cell that keeps dehydrating after the plasmolysis has started ($t > t_p$). In this stage, since the cell membrane has
159 detached from the cell wall, as shown in Fig. 1b, the dehydration process was simulated by imposing water evaporation
160 on the cell lateral sides too. Therefore, in Figure 2b, the lateral sides of the simulated cell are free to move and the cell
161 volume significantly reduces in the reported three successive times after plasmolysis has occurred, following the real
162 trend measured in Fig. 1d. As a consequence of the dehydration, a pattern of curved liquid streamlines (reported in red
163 in Fig. 2) arises inside the cell and increases during the analyzed process. This gives a fluid dynamic argument for the
164 observed 3D movements of cell nucleus during dehydration, also because dehydration induces a rearrangement of the
165 cytoskeleton that weakens the constraints keeping the nucleus fixed. In conclusion, the nucleus starts to move in 3D and
166 rotate within the cell, thus providing optical access to its 2D projections. This effect can be observed and exploited even
167 before the plasmolysis event, as confirmed by the experimental results in the next sections.

168

169 **Fig. 2. Geometry of the domain considered in finite-element DNS of cell dehydration at increasing values of time.**

170 **a** (Supplementary Movie 2) Cell undergoing dehydration, before plasmolysis, and reducing its height along z-direction.

171 **b** (Supplementary Movie 3) Cell undergoing dehydration, after plasmolysis, and reducing its lateral sizes along x- and

172 y-directions. Liquid streamlines are displayed in red in (a,b).

173

174 2.3. 3D tracking of the nuclei

175 In Figure 3a, we show two typical examples of QPMs observed during cell dehydration, respectively at times 5 h and 17

176 h. We highlight in red the cell walls of three cells and in green, cyan, and yellow the corresponding nuclear membranes.

177 We use the centroid method³³ to calculate the transverse position (x_N, y_N) of each nucleus (blue dot) and the transverse

178 position (x_C, y_C) of the corresponding cell (red dot). For each nucleus, in Figure 3b we report the transverse positions

179 relative to the centroids of the outer cells. Indeed, as shown in Figure 3a, cells within the FoV move slightly upwards

180 throughout the recorded sequence. However, the cell wall always retains its initial shape, so the relative transverse

181 positions allows neglecting this effect. Moreover, the holographic technique allows recovering the axial position of a

182 sample by adopting autofocusing criteria, e.g. through the Tamura coefficient optimization³³. Therefore, in Figure 3b,

183 we also report the axial position z_N of each nucleus with respect to a reference axial position z_0 that corresponds to the

184 lower surface of the layer of the onion cells. In Figure 3c, we show on the same plot the 3D tracking of the second

185 nucleus, which is a synthesis of the information reported in Fig. 3b. For the sake of clarity, we show one position every

186 30 minutes, corresponding to a time downsampling of the plots in Fig. 3b, and we highlight the time the plasmolysis

187 event takes place, $t_{p2} = 12.2$ h. Moreover, we report the corresponding 2D tracks in the xy- and xz-planes. As indicated

188 by the colorbar, different dot colors correspond to different times. Supplementary Movie 4 shows the time-lapse QPMs

189 and the complete 3D tracking of the three nuclei under test.

190 Of course, the movements of the nuclei within their cells appear to be affected by both translations and rotations. A full

191 analysis of typical nuclear movements is reported in Fig. 3d and Fig. 3e and shown in Supplementary Movie 4. In

192 particular, in Figure 3d we plot the temporal trend of the observed area, A_N , of each nucleus. The changes in the

193 projected areas highlight a rotation around an axis that lies in the xy-plane. Instead, in Figure 3e we plot the temporal

194 trend of the orientation of each nucleus with respect to the x-axis, which underlines a rotation around the optical z axis.

195 Vertical lines in Fig. 3b, Fig. 3d and Fig. 3e indicate the plasmolysis event for the three cells under test.

196

197 **Fig. 3.** (Supplementary Movie 4) **Movements of the nuclei induced by dehydration.** **a** Two QPMs at different times
 198 with the cell walls highlighted in red and the corresponding nuclear membranes in green, cyan and yellow. Dots are the
 199 centroids of the nuclei (blue) and of their cells (red). **b** Tracking of the three nuclei. From left to right, the first two plots
 200 are the nuclear transverse position (x_N, y_N) with respect to the cell transverse position (x_C, y_C), while the third plot is the
 201 nuclear axial position z_N with respect to the reference axial position z_0 , which corresponds to the lower surface of the
 202 layer of onion cells. **c** 3D tracking of the second nucleus, with the corresponding 2D tracks in the xy - and xz -planes. As
 203 indicated by the colorbar, different dot colors correspond to different times, including the time of plasmolysis $t_{p2} = 12.2$
 204 h. For the sake of clarity, we show one position every 30 minutes, corresponding to a time downsampling of the plots in
 205 (b). **d** Temporal trend of the area of the three nuclei A_N in the xy -plane. **e** Temporal trend of the orientation of the three
 206 nuclei with respect to the x -axis. In (b, d, e), the vertical lines highlight the plasmolysis of the analyzed cells.

207

208 Note that the roto-translations of the cells' nuclei can be already observed at the beginning of the dehydration process.

209 As shown in Figure 1c, although plasmolysis occurs only when the rate of aqueous loss is maximum, the increase of

210 contrast and in turn the decrease of turgor pressure is continuous within the observation window. Therefore, even when
211 the cell membrane has not detached from the cell wall, the reduction of the turgor pressure causes internal cell flows
212 and a non-negligible relaxation of the intermediate filaments. As a consequence, the nucleus can start moving within the
213 cell. This is a very important property. Indeed, in the following we describe how to exploit this induced rotation process
214 to perform phase contrast tomography of the nucleus, in order to estimate the associated refractive index distribution
215 and 3D morphometry at sub-nuclear level. The temporal interval in which we use QPMs for the tomographic
216 reconstruction of the nuclei is highlighted by two black vertical lines in Fig. 4a, overlapped to the global normalized
217 contrast. It goes from 1.5 h to 4 h, i.e. much before the plasmolysis (vertical violet line at 12 h). This means that, to use
218 the tomographic tool in order to perform a 3D analysis of the nucleus of a plant cell, plasmolysis is not a required event,
219 and one can operate in a time window of total reversibility for the cell. Therefore, in principle one could induce a
220 controlled dehydration, make the tomographic reconstruction of the nucleus when the cell just starts to become flaccid
221 and then bring it back to the initial turgid state by hydration without any damage for the sample.

222

223 **2.4. Rolling angle tracking**

224 Figure 4b shows the first QPM of the sequence we use for tomography, which corresponds to the first black line in Fig.
225 4a. A violet box indicates the Region Of Interest (ROI) containing the analyzed nucleus. For each frame of the sequence
226 within the black lines in Fig. 4a, an ellipse, having axes equal to the major and minor orthogonal sizes of the nucleus in
227 that frame, is used for image segmentation. Figure 4c shows zoom in details of the ROI, extracted from three QPMs
228 containing the same nucleus that rotates during the observation interval, along with the corresponding ellipses. The
229 nucleus is extracted from each image, centered with respect to its centroid and rotated in the image plane xy to align the
230 major axis to the x -direction, as reported in Fig. 4d. In this way, the nucleus rotation can be detected from the variation
231 of the minor axes' lengths, highlighted by the blue lines in Fig. 4d, while the major axis keeps fixed. Figure 4e reports
232 the minor axes' lengths in each frame of the sequence, showing a sinusoidal trend and providing four local extremes
233 $m = \{1,2,3,4\}$ (colored dots). According to the shape and the variation of the segmented phase maps in Fig. 4c and Fig.
234 4d, the rotation of the nucleus appears as the rotation of a plate around an axis parallel to its major face. Therefore, we
235 assume that the nucleus makes a rotation of 90° between two successive extremes. We exploit this behavior to recover
236 the unknown rolling angles employing the method proposed in ref. 34, based on the 3D ellipsoid fitting. The procedure
237 developed to estimate the rotation angles is detailed in the Materials and Methods section. The rotation angles, θ_k ,
238 estimated using the angle tracking algorithm are indicated in Fig. 4h by circles and crosses. As shown in Figure 4h,
239 according to the choice of the axes of the simulated ellipsoid, the difference between the recovered rolling angles
240 corresponding to the global extreme points is an entire multiple of 90° . Therefore, we can estimate that between the
241 global extremes ($m = 1$ and $m = 4$) a 270° rotation occurs (Fig. 4h). Instead, $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ cannot be considered
242 the points in which the rotations at 90° and 180° occur, since they are only local extrema, not corresponding to a global
243 minimum or maximum. For this reason, after ordering the fitted angles, we exclude the images corresponding to angles
244 in the local extreme points since they are indeterminate. In Figure 4h, the excluded data are represented by colored
245 crosses. The angle tracking algorithm described above and in the Materials and Methods section is summarized in
246 Supplementary Movie 5. The proposed technique allows recovering the unknown rolling angles of the plant cells'
247 nuclei without having any prior information.

248

249 **Fig. 4.** (Supplementary Movie 5) **Rolling angle recovery method** (see also Materials and Methods). **a** Global image
 250 contrast normalized between 0 and 1, with overlapped in red the logistic fitting. The vertical black lines delimit the
 251 interval of frames used to perform the tomographic reconstruction of the analyzed nucleus (from 1.5 h to 4 h), while the
 252 vertical violet line corresponds to the plasmolysis of the surrounding cell (12 h). **b** QPM at 1.5 h with highlighted in
 253 violet the ROI containing the analyzed nucleus ($36.6 \mu\text{m} \times 36.6 \mu\text{m}$). **c** ROIs taken from three QPMs, with overlapped
 254 in red the contours of the elliptic binary masks. **d** Segmented QPMs in (c), centered and rotated to align the minor axes
 255 (in blue) along the y-direction of the reference system. At the top of each image, the corresponding recovered rolling
 256 angle is reported. Scale bar is $5 \mu\text{m}$. **e** Minor axes' lengths l_k of the elliptic binary masks of the same nucleus in the
 257 various frames k . The four colored dots are the extreme points m of the curve. **f** Silhouette of the nucleus simulated as
 258 an ellipsoid, according to the shape and the size of its segmented phase maps. **g** Three projections of the ellipsoid in (f)
 259 in the xy-plane, obtained by rotating it around the x-direction at the angles reported at the top of each image and by
 260 summing along the z-direction. Red lines are their minor axes. Scale bar is $5 \mu\text{m}$. **h** Minor axes' lengths l of the
 261 projections of the numerical ellipsoid in (f) versus the simulated rolling angles β (red line). Circles and crosses are the
 262 recovered rolling angles θ_k corresponding to the minor axes' lengths l_k in (e). For the sake of clarity, only one of the
 263 two possible determinations of the estimated angles for $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ is shown in (h) by colored crossed. Due to
 264 the ambiguity, such angles are not considered here for PCT.

265

266 It requires the recognition of at least one minimum-maximum or maximum-minimum transition in the curve of minor
 267 axes' lengths, because we use these extreme values to simulate the rotation of an ellipsoid with the same size of the

268 segmented nucleus. Moreover, the nucleus must rotate around a single rotation axis. In the proposed example, this
269 property is satisfied because the length of major axes is always the same, i.e. $L = 23.44 \mu\text{m}$, and the nucleus has never a
270 rigorously circular projection in the various frames, as confirmed by the comparison between the major axis length and
271 the values in Fig. 4e. In addition to the rolling angles, by using this method we obtain the segmented and centered phase
272 maps, aligned to have the rotation around the x direction, as shown in Fig. 4d. Combining angle tracking and 3D
273 centroid tracking, we can follow the 3D roto-translation of the nuclei within the FoV fulfilling the abovementioned
274 conditions. In the cases in which a sufficient number of views of the nucleus is available, the set of centered phase maps
275 and the associated angles constitute the input of the filtered back-projection algorithm⁴³ to reconstruct the 3D tomogram
276 of a plant cell nucleus.

277

278 **2.5. Phase Contrast Tomography of the Nucleus**

279 In Figure 5 we report the results of the 3D tomographic pipeline for the two analyzed nuclei. The first row reports the
280 reconstruction of the nucleus in Fig. 4. In Figure 5a we show the rolling angles recovered by using the method
281 described above. To reconstruct this nucleus, we used 24 of the 26 recorded frames, since we excluded two frames
282 corresponding to the undetermined local extreme points, as previously discussed. For this reason, the plot in Fig. 5a
283 exhibits two discontinuities. The two leftmost images in Figure 5b show two central slices of the 3D reconstructed
284 nucleus, cut along two orthogonal directions. The tomographic technique allows to obtain the 3D spatial distribution of
285 refractive index (RI). In the leftmost slice in Figure 5b, it is clear the presence of a localized region at the highest RI
286 values, which can be identified as the nucleolus. Therefore, we segment the nucleus in nucleoplasm and nucleolus by
287 finding the corresponding interval of RI values. The third image in Figure 5b is an iso-levels representation of the
288 nucleus, in which the nucleolus is highlighted in red. Finally, in Figure 5c the histograms of the RI values of the nucleus
289 and nucleolus are reported. It is clear that, the segmented object (nucleolus) is well defined and separated from the
290 surrounding medium (nucleoplasm) because of the unimodality of its RI distribution. In order to confirm the correct
291 identification of the segmented object as the nucleolus, we compared its shape and relative size (with respect to the
292 whole nuclear size) with the values that can be inferred from the images reported in literature, recorded by a confocal
293 microscope⁴⁴, a transmission electron microscope^{45,46}, and an atomic force microscope⁴⁷. Noteworthy, we found very
294 good agreement between the result obtained using the proposed QPI approach and the other gold standard methods.
295 However, one of the main advantages of phase-contrast tomography with respect to more conventional imaging
296 techniques is the possibility to measure quantitative 3D morphological features and RI statistics of the sample. In this
297 case, dehydration induces phase-contrast enhancement and rotation, allowing such quantification at sub-nuclear level.
298 In the first column of Table 1, some of these quantities are reported for the example of Fig. 5a to Fig. 5c. In particular,
299 an important biological parameter is the dry mass m_d , i.e. the mass of the cell without the aqueous content. It can be
300 calculated from the reconstructed tomogram^{22,48} as follows:

$$301 \quad m_d = \frac{(\bar{n} - n_w)V}{\alpha}, \quad (1)$$

302 where \bar{n} is the mean value of RI, $n_w = 1.334$ is the RI of water, V is the volume and α is the refraction increment⁴⁹,
303 reported for proteins and DNA to be $\alpha \approx 0.2 \text{ ml g}^{-1}$. In order to obtain a reliable tomogram, the maximum illumination
304 angle should be at least 180° . However, sometimes the sample does not complete a 180° rotation in the recorded
305 holographic sequence.

306

Table 1. Quantitative measurements in 3D reconstructed tomograms of plant cells nuclei.

	Cell 1	Cell 2
Nuclear Volume [μm^3]	1377.42	1085.82
Nuclear Equivalent Radius [μm]	6.90	6.38
Nuclear 1 st Principal Axis [μm]	19.61	19.22
Nuclear 2 nd Principal Axis [μm]	13.89	14.97
Nuclear 3 rd Principal Axis [μm]	6.98	5.26
Nuclear Average RI	1.43	1.43
Nuclear Standard Deviation RI	0.04	0.04
Nuclear Minimum RI	1.33	1.33
Nuclear Maximum RI	1.54	1.53
Nuclear Dry Mass [pg]	640.87	514.35
Nucleolar Volume [μm^3]	50.25	40.12
Nucleolar Equivalent Radius [μm]	2.29	2.12
Nucleolar 1 st Principal Axis [μm]	4.95	4.53
Nucleolar 2 nd Principal Axis [μm]	3.96	3.77
Nucleolar 3 rd Principal Axis [μm]	3.56	3.25
Nucleolar Average RI	1.48	1.48
Nucleolar Standard Deviation RI	0.02	0.02
Nucleolar Minimum RI	1.38	1.40
Nucleolar Maximum RI	1.54	1.53
Nucleolar Dry Mass [pg]	23.37	19.01
Nucleolar-Nuclear Volume Ratio [%]	3.65	3.70

307

308 An example is reported in Fig. 4d to Fig. 4f. To reconstruct this nucleus, we used all the 17 recorded frames, recovering
309 a maximum rolling angle of about 130°. In fact, if the maximum rolling angle is lower than 180°, the curve of minor
310 axes' lengths contains only global extreme points, so the final check about the local extreme points described above is
311 useless. For this reason, unlike Fig. 5a, in Fig. 5d no discontinuity can be observed. Despite the angular discontinuities,
312 the tomogram in Fig. 5b has a higher quality because the maximum recovered rolling angle is about 300°, meaning that
313 more information is available for the reconstruction. However, although the reconstruction quality in Fig. 5d to Fig. 5f
314 is lower due to the limited maximum rolling angle, we measured RI statistical features close to those of the first
315 nucleus, as reported in the second column of Table 1, and, more important, we were still able to segment the nucleolus
316 from the surrounding nucleoplasm. Finally, we underline that this second nucleus was extracted from another
317 holographic sequence, but even in this case the tomographic window was placed in time much before the critical event,
318 i.e. the plasmolysis. Supplementary Movie 6 summarizes the results reported in Fig. 5 and offers a complete view of the

348 recordings during a previously determined optimal time window within which the process is reversible, i.e. before
349 plasmolysis starts. Dehydration increases the phase-contrast between the cell nucleus, cytoskeleton and the surrounding
350 cytoplasm, thus enhancing our ability to observe tiny subcellular structures through a limited sensitivity phase-contrast
351 process. Thus, we observed cytoplasm circulation, intracellular transport phenomena, along with nucleus 3D
352 movements and rotations. Such movements should be traced back to the changes in the hydrodynamic equilibrium state
353 and the intrinsic cell reorganization upon dehydration starts, in agreement with the simplified model and the
354 corresponding 3D finite-element numerical simulation. Combining centroid and angle tracking proved to be effective in
355 retrieving tomographic maps of the cells' nuclei. Studying the tomograms and the refractive index statistics allowed us
356 isolating the nucleolus from the nucleoplasm in the 3D tomograms under analysis, and to measure its refractive index,
357 3D morphometry, biovolume, and dry mass. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first label-free refractive index
358 and biovolume quantification at sub-nuclear level, made possible here by the "virtual" increment in system sensitivity
359 that allowed us to accurately 3D track and refocus the nuclei in each frame of the time-lapse sequence. The recovered
360 morphological information and the size ratio between the nucleolus and nucleoplasm are in good agreement with values
361 reported in literature referring to more conventional invasive techniques⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷. In the case of onion epidermal cells, we
362 found that the cell nucleus has higher refractive index than the cytoplasm, and that the nucleolus has higher refractive
363 index than the nucleoplasm. Isolating the nucleolus through PCT and thus measuring its quantitative features (see Table
364 1) could be pivotal in future perspectives to infer information about the content of genetic material in some cell lines.
365 Possible developments of the method will address how to reinforce analysis tools, relying on machine learning to better
366 analyze the tomograms and extract meaningful 3D features from the main sub-cellular and sub-nuclear components. It
367 is worth pointing out how DH imaging allowed us to analyze and model the whole dehydration process towards
368 plasmolysis. In particular, from the sole analysis of the normalized contrast of Fig. 1c we were able to deduce useful
369 information on the reduction of turgor pressure and how this process develops in time, which is well fitted by a logistic
370 curve. Moreover, we found that the derivative of the fitting curve has a peak in correspondence with the breaking event
371 of the process, i.e. the convex plasmolysis with the detachment of the cell membrane from the cell wall. Even more
372 important, we demonstrated that, in order to reach the aforementioned tomographic results, plasmolysis is not a required
373 event, and one can operate in a time window of total reversibility for the cell. Therefore, in principle one could induce a
374 controlled dehydration, make the tomographic reconstruction of the nucleus when the cell just starts to become flaccid
375 and then bring it back to the initial turgid state by hydration. The presented results are a proof of concept of the
376 possibility to exploit a natural biological process as dehydration in a functional way, i.e. as a sort tool that allows 3D
377 tomographic imaging of nuclei in plant cells using a conventional setup. Thanks to this fascinating possibility, we have
378 achieved nucleus PCT, and we have clearly identified and quantitatively characterized the nucleolus. Although this has
379 been applied here solely to epidermal onion cells, we expect it can be easily extended to all similar plant cells. In these
380 cases, the optimal observation time window in which rotation occurs in a reversible modality is expected to change and
381 should be estimated first. Moreover, since dehydration can be affected by processes of cell aging, estimating the optimal
382 time window could be used as effective diagnostic tool to monitor plants' health and its related biological processes. In
383 fact, dehydration is a typical stressing factor for plants in situation of scarce water resources. The approach
384 demonstrated here could improve the investigation in plant biology by a non-destructively controlled procedure and by
385 means of a conventional label-free holographic microscope able to furnish 3D quantitative analysis at sub-nuclear level.
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387
388

389 4. Materials and Methods

390 4.1. Digital holography processing

391 Let H be the digital hologram captured in off-axis configuration (Fig. 6). This is the coherent superposition of the object
392 beam, O , and the reference beam, R :

$$393 \quad H = |R + O|^2 = |R|^2 + |O|^2 + R^*O + RO^* \quad (2)$$

394 The angle between O and R allows decoupling the object image from the twin image and the zero-th order term by
395 trivially demodulating Equation 2. In the case the object of interest is captured out of focus, numerical propagation of
396 the demodulated hologram, H_d , allows retrieving the object complex amplitude in the best focus plane, $C = P_{z_F}\{H_d; z_F\}$,
397 where $P_z\{\dots\}$ is the propagation operator that solves the diffraction integral⁵². The best-focus distance, z_F , maximizes a
398 proper contrast metrics, namely the Tamura coefficient³³ of the sample phase-contrast map $\psi_O = \arg\{C\}$.

399 **Fig. 6. Experimental setup.** HWP1/ HWP2: half wave plates at wavelength 532nm. PBS: polarizing beam splitter.
400 M1/M2: mirrors. MO1/MO2: microscope objectives. BS: beam splitter.
401
402

403 4.2. Experimental setup

404 The off-axis DH setup is based on a Mach-Zehnder interferometer scheme with two coherent beams generated by a
405 laser source of wavelength $\lambda=532$ nm (Fig. 6). The laser spot is divided into two beams by a Polarizer Beam Splitter
406 prism (PBS), where the transmission beam is set as the object beam, and the reflected beam is set as a reference. One
407 half-wave plate is placed in front of the PBS to adjust the splitting ratio of the two beams, and another half-wave plate is
408 located behind of the PBS to adjust the polarization state of this beam. Living onion epidermal cells are prepared and
409 loaded in between two pieces of glass slides and placed in the path of object beam, so that its amplitude and phase
410 information can modulate the object wavefront. After passing through the beam splitter prism (BS), the object beam and
411 reference beam with an angle between them are combined and generate an interference pattern, i.e. the off-axis digital
412 hologram. Two identical microscope objectives with 25 \times magnification and 0.4 NA are used to provide a 26.43 \times
413 overall imaging system magnification, measured using a USAF-1951 resolution target. A CCD camera with 1280 \times 960
414 square pixels with 4.5 μ m pixel pitch is employed to record the digital holograms. Thus, the pixel size in the image
415 plane is $\Delta x=\Delta y=0.17$ μ m. In the optical setup, the two spherical waves from the object beam and reference beam have
416 the same curvature. The effective spatial resolution in the image plane, measured using a USAF test target, is 0.24 μ m.
417 The holographic setup captures a FoV=0.036 mm². The setup is conceived to be minimally invasive for the sample
418 layers, so that we kept the beam power on the sample plane lower than 0.021 mW during the entire experiment.

419

4.3. Estimation of rotation angles

420 Let l_k be the minor axes' lengths, with $k=1, \dots, N$ being the index of a generic frame and N the number of frames. Let f_m
421 be the index of a generic frame containing an extreme point, with $m=1, \dots, M$, where M is the number of extreme points.
422 As shown in Figure 4f, we generate a numerical ellipsoid, whose axes are defined as the major axis (along the
423 x-direction), the maximum minor axis (along the y-direction), and the minimum minor axis (along the z-direction) of
424 the ellipses used to segment the phase maps. Therefore, this ellipsoid approximates the silhouette of the rolling nucleus.
425 We simulate the rotation of the ellipsoid from 0° to 360° around the x-direction. For each simulated rolling angle, β , we
426 sum the values of the rotated ellipsoid along the z-direction to generate its projections, which have an elliptic shape in
427 the xy-plane. Figure 4g shows three of these ellipses with the corresponding angles of projection, highlighting in red
428 their minor axes. The so-obtained ellipses always have the same major axis, i.e. the major axis of the elliptic binary
429 masks, while their minor axes' lengths, l , take intermediate values from the maximum minor axis to the minimum minor
430 axis measured in the elliptic binary masks. In Figure 4h, the dependence of the simulated rolling angles β from the
431 minor axes lengths l of the projected ellipses is plotted with a red line. The simulated ellipses in Fig. 4d are directly
432 comparable with the elliptic binary masks in Fig. 4g. Therefore, for each measured minor axis length, l_k , from the curve
433 $\beta(l)$ we extract the corresponding fitted rolling angles β_k , with $k=1, \dots, N$. The fitted angles, β_k , are in the 0° - 90° interval
434 and, for $k=1, \dots, N$, they follow a trend similar to the trend of the minor axes lengths, l_k , in Fig. 4e. Therefore, we
435 reorganize them in a crescent order by using the property discussed above, i.e. whenever the curve in Fig. 4e passes an
436 extreme point m , the nucleus accumulates an additional 90° rotation. In this way, we recover the rolling angles, θ_k ,
437 which we show as circles in Fig. 4g, also highlighting the extreme points of Fig. 4e. Moreover, at the top of the three
438 segmented phase maps in Fig. 4d, we report the corresponding recovered rolling angles.

440

4.4. Sample preparation

441 Samples of living onion epidermal cells were prepared from fresh onions with intact and undamaged fibrous roots.
442 During sample preparation, the fourth layer of fleshy scale leaves from the center was used to prepare a single layer of
443 onion epidermal cells. Then, the selected single-layer onion epidermal cells were loaded in between the two glass slides.
444 During the whole experiment, the environment temperature in the laboratory was kept to 20°C , and the humidity was
445 maintained at 35%. Digital holograms of the onion epidermal cells were recorded under darkroom conditions.

447

4.5. Measure of the cytoplasm refractive index

448 Fresh rooted onions were bought the morning of the experiment. The roots were immersed in water for 8 hours. 20
449 single-layer onion skins were peeled out, each with $2\text{ cm} \times 5\text{ cm}$ area. Layers were stacked, gently crushed in a test
450 tube, and then centrifugated to obtain the cell cytosol. A two-layer ashless filter paper was used to filter the cytosol out.
451 The filtered cytosol was put in a sealed test tube and made stand for one hour. The overall procedure has been repeated
452 15 times to obtain enough fluid for the measure. The obtained fluid was injected inside a $100\mu\text{m}$ high
453 Polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) microfluidic channel and a DH was captured. Conventional DH processing was
454 applied to obtain the phase of the liquid. A reference hologram was captured after filling a clean PMMA microfluidic
455 channel with water. Since the channel height and its own refractive index, $n_{\text{PMMA}} = 1.490$, did not change between the
456 measures, comparing the phase values provided the indirect estimation of the fluid refractive index, i.e. $n_c = 1.368$,
457 which is in good agreement with the value reported in literature⁵⁰.

459

460 **Acknowledgements**

461 Z.W. is thankful to Beijing TaiGeek Technology Co., Ltd for the permission to use their holographic equipment.

462

463 **Author contributions**

464 Z.W. performed the holographic experiments, D.P., V.B., P.M. and Z.W. designed and performed the numerical analysis of the
465 experimental results and prepared the data reported in the paper. M.V. and P.L.M. contributed about numerical fluidic analysis. All
466 the authors contributed to conceptual interpretation of the results, P.F. and P.L.M. conceived and supervised the project. All authors
467 contributed in writing and participated in the discussions on the paper.

468

469 **Conflict of interest**

470 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

471

472 **Supplementary information**

473 Supplementary information accompanies the manuscript on the *Light: Science & Applications* website

474 (<http://www.nature.com/lisa>).

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